

Study to investigate the national and institutional policies and approaches to education for environmental sustainability (EES)

Case Study Portugal

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Name of the initiative: Curriculum Flexibility and Autonomy (Autonomia e Flexibilidade Curricular (AFC))

Synopsis of the methodical approach in this case study: Based on the guidelines for this research, we first conducted desktop research and developed a list of potential and adequate interviewees and focus group participants, aiming to include relevant representatives from different actors groups involved in and working with AFC, i.e.: (i) governmental entities (Directorate-General of Education (DGE); (ii) the executing organ of the ministry of education), (iii) independent entities with advisory functions (Portuguese Council of Education (CNE), (iv) educational experts like researchers; (v) school representatives and teachers, (vi) as well as representatives of NGOs / CSO like the Portuguese association in charge of the Eco-Schools Programme (ABAE) and the Portuguese confederation of parents' associations. Most invitations sent were responded positively, and since some institutions decided to bring more than one interviewee, the total sample comprises 18 participants (see Table A1 in Annex II), of which 7 participated in the final focus group (see Table A3, Annex II). All interviews and the focus group were recorded and transcribed, summarising the main aspects of each conversation held. The collected data was then confronted with literature from the desktop research as well as with the personal experience of the national experts' team and triangulated to answer this template's questions. In order to facilitate the integration of interviews and/ or the focus group in the text, we propose to use the anonymized form of hashtag and number as of Table A1, e.g. #1 for participant 1 in our sample list.

Note: Please note that *Annex I* provides key acronyms, *Annex II* includes the detailed information about the sample (full participant list, n=18), and interviews listed by affiliation and focus group participants; *Annex III* includes the interview guide and focus group presentation.

1.1. National context

1.1.1. How does the selected initiative fit within the national context? To what extent is the initiative needed? Does it address particular needs or gaps present within the national context? Does it contribute to particular national policies and goals, and if so, how?¹

AFC is a governmental initiative about curricular redesign that began in 2017 with a pilot phase in which the initiative was tested and evaluated². The initiative is also part of an educational reform process that includes the national document “Students’ Profile by the End of Compulsory Schooling” (Perfil dos Alunos à Saída da Escolaridade Obrigatória, PASEO)³, which constitutes an important pillar to AFC. AFC became mandatory legislation⁴ in 2018 and is designed to respond to SDG 4 (“quality education”) and it was launched as a new political agenda of the new ministry of education (now in its second mandate).

AFC is part of a legal framework that addresses a new educational vision, resulting from a wide consultation process, conducted in 2016, involving the different stakeholders of the Portuguese education system (“*Currículo para o Século XXI: competências, conhecimentos e valores numa escolaridade de 12 anos*”)⁵, to which was added a special attention to the voices of the students (“*Currículo para o Século XXI: A Voz dos Alunos*”)⁶.

The conducted consultation process had identified the following key problems^{see 5} of the national education system: a) high retention rate of students from age 15 and upper (31%); b) school failure associated with the (low) levels of schooling of the parents (mothers); c) non-articulated curriculum programs, leading to a

¹ Please see the following for more information on how to assess the need/scalability/transferability of the initiative: Nesta (n.d.). Evidence of impact: Making the case. Available at: https://media.nesta.org.uk/documents/skills_evidence_of_impact.pdf [Accessed 2021.04.09]

² OECD (2018). Curriculum Flexibility and Autonomy in Portugal - an OECD review. Available at:

https://afc.dge.mec.pt/sites/default/files/2020-02/OECD_2018_Curriculum_Flexibility_and_Autonomy_in_Portugal_an_OECD_review.pdf [accessed 04/05/2021].

³ Directorate-General for Education (DGE) (2017), “Students’ Profile at the End of Compulsory Education”. Available at: https://www.dge.mec.pt/sites/default/files/Curriculo/Projeto_Autonomia_e_Flexibilidade/perfil_dos_alunos.pdf [accessed 04/05/2021]

⁴ Government of Portugal, “Decree-Law on Primary and secondary school curriculum and guidelines for learning assessment [Currículo dos Ensinos Básico e Secundário e Princípios Orientadores da Avaliação das Aprendizagens]”, 06 July 2018 (55/2018). Available at:

https://www.dge.mec.pt/sites/default/files/Curriculo/AFC/dl_55_2018_afc.pdf [accessed 04/05/2021].

⁵ Directorate-General of Education (DGE) (2016). Conferência Currículo para o Século XXI: competências, conhecimentos e valores numa escolaridade de 12 anos [Curricula conference for the 21st century: competencies, knowledge and values for 12 years schooling]. Available at:

<https://www.dge.mec.pt/conferencia-curriculo-para-o-seculo-xxi-competencias-conhecimentos-e-valores-numa-escolaridade-de-12> [accessed 04/05/2021].

⁶ Directorate-General for Education (DGE) (2016). Conferência Currículo para o Século XXI: A Voz dos Alunos [Curricula conference for the 21st century: The voice of the students]. Available at: <https://www.dge.mec.pt/conferencia-curriculo-para-o-seculo-xxi-voz-dos-alunos> [accessed 04/05/2021].

desynchronized education system, having “a 19th century school, with 20th century teachers and 21st century students” (Interviewee #7).

From the students’ perspective^{see 6}, the identified key problems were: a) little or no pedagogical differentiation (little use of different pedagogical methods and approaches, usually focusing on traditional methods limiting collaboration and participation); b) excessive focus on the teacher; and c) overuse of expositive/ passive pedagogical practices, where students are reduced to mere assimilators of information.

Consensus was thus reached on the necessary change of approach to the national curriculum - and a common vision (and goal) emerged: to project a 12 years’ schooling path with a differentiated teaching, for an active and democratic citizenship, promoting a set of essential learnings and key competences for the 21st century.

As concrete outputs of this consultation process, a legal framework of governmental decree-laws and orders was then designed to address this vision. One key instrument is the ‘Students’ Profile at the End of Compulsory Education’ (*Perfil dos Alunos à Saída da Escolaridade Obrigatória*, PASEO)^{see 3}, addressing students’ fields of knowledge, values and competences.

The AFC initiative comprehends PASEO and the below listed documents that constitute the above mentioned legal framework, as a reform of the Portuguese education system for compulsory education. This framework includes AFC, as a specific diploma that regulates curricula in primary and secondary education; guidelines for inclusive schools, launching the whole school vision and approach; the essential learnings to be reached in each school level and cycle; the citizenship education strategy, where EES is included; and the innovation plans, for schools that intend to go further than the 25% of curricular autonomy and flexibility:

- ‘Curriculum of the Primary and Secondary Education and Guiding Principles for Assessing Learnings accordingly with PASEO’ (DL 55/2018)⁷;
- Inclusive education, which establishes the inclusive school regime (IE), (DL 54/2018)⁸;
- ‘Essential Learnings in Primary Education’ (*Aprendizagens Essenciais no Ensino Básico - 1º, 2º e 3º Ciclos*, AE)⁹;
- ‘National Strategy for Citizenship Education’ (*Estratégia Nacional de Educação para a Cidadania*, ENEC)¹⁰ and Guidelines for Essential Learnings in its 10 domains, with a specific one for EES; and

⁷ Government of Portugal, “Decree-Law on Primary and secondary school curriculum and guidelines for learning assessment [Currículo dos Ensinos Básico e Secundário e Princípios Orientadores da Avaliação das Aprendizagens]”, 06 July 2018 (55/2018). Available at:

https://www.dge.mec.pt/sites/default/files/Curriculo/AFC/dl_55_2018_afc.pdf [accessed 04/05/2021].

⁸ Presidency of the Council of Ministers in Portugal, “Decree-Law on the legal regime for inclusive education”, 06 July 2018 (54/2018). Available at: <https://dre.pt/application/conteudo/115652961> [accessed 04/05/2021].

⁹ Directorate-General of Education, “Order on Essential Learning (Aprendizagens Essenciais - AE) that ratifies Decree-Law 55/2018 of 6 July 2018”, 19 July 2018 (nr. 6944-A/2018). Available at: <https://www.dge.mec.pt/aprendizagens-essenciais-ensino-basico> and <https://dre.pt/application/file/a/115742277> [accessed 04/05/2021].

¹⁰ Ministry of Education of Portugal (2017), National Strategy for Citizenship Education (*Estratégia Nacional para a Educação de Cidadania* (ENEC)). Available at: <https://cidadania.dge.mec.pt/sites/default/files/pdfs/national-strategy-citizenship-education.pdf> [accessed 04/05/2021].

- 'Innovation Plans' (*Planos de Inovação, PI*)¹¹, for schools that adopted more than 25% of autonomous curriculum design in the pilot phase of AFC (Project AFC (PAFC)), see 1.2.3).

The above listed instruments were understood as a coherent basis to launch the vision of an education for the XXI century, much aligned with the values and competencies expected in key areas, comprehending citizenship, human development and sustainable development, as also highlighted by some focus group participants[#] (interviewees #1 and #12 - see Table A1).

The EES related competencies and essential learnings, as described in this study's first phase (Portuguese National Report, item 1.1.2), are the following:

Competencies	Essential Learnings
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Personal consciousness, development and autonomy ● Healthy sense of life and living environment ● Communication skills ● Interpersonal relationship ● Reasoning and problem solving ● Critical and creative thinking ● Artistic and aesthetic sensitivity ● Technical and technological knowledge 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Global interdisciplinary view - understands the concept of sustainability; ● Systemic interdependence view - is aware that actions influence environment; ● Responsibility - understands rights and duties as citizen towards environment; ● Protective/ conservationist and temporal view - adopts 'resources preservation' behaviours in respect for life/ biodiversity conservation and legacy for future generations; ● Integrity view - adopts behaviors aimed at self and other humans and other animals and living beings integrity, health and welfare.

¹¹ Government of Portugal, "Ordinance on Innovation Plans assuming management of over 25% of the total workload (basic curricula)", 11th June 2019 (181/2019). Available at: <https://dre.pt/application/conteudo/122541299> [accessed 05/05/2021].

1.2. Initiative

1.2.1. Who is responsible for the design, funding and implementation of the initiative? At what level has the initiative been implemented? What is the main target group of the initiative? When and where was the initiative first implemented? Are there plans to continue the initiative, and if so, for how long?

The Portuguese Government, namely the Ministry of Education, through the General-Directorate of Education (DGE), is responsible for design, funding, support to implementation, monitoring and evaluation of the AFC initiative.

DGE has a coordinating role in the AFC implementation, with a specific team assigned (*Equipa de Avaliação, Monitorização e Desenvolvimento Curricular, AMDC*), currently with 17 technicians (full-time teachers assigned for the purpose).

AFC, as established in the Decree-Law no 55/2018^{see 4}, was set up to be implemented at national level, by all public and private schools within compulsory education (from primary education to secondary education).

The first (school) year of implementation was in 2018-2019, covering 811 school clusters and non-grouped schools¹² (*Agrupamentos de Escolas e Escolas Não Agrupadas, AE/ENA*), in a total of 6.263¹³ establishments of the public network, and 1.482¹⁴ schools of the private network. This implementation was set up progressively, year by year within each cycle, as determined by the Decree-Law 55/2018^{see 6}, being complete in the present school year (2021-2022).

To support AFC implementation (namely follow, monitor and evaluate the application of the Decree-Laws 55/2018^{see 4} and 54/2018^{see 8}), the Portuguese government determined, through the Legislative Order 9726/2018¹⁵, the creation of a national coordination team, assisted by a technical team, and five regional teams, covering the national continental territory (the Portuguese islands groups of Azores and Madeira were included with two representatives in the National Coordination Team). All public training centers for educational professionals (*Centros de Formação de Associação de Escola, CFAE* - 91 in total) were also called to participate, with each of its teams reinforced with one technician coming from teachers' mobility (released from teaching

¹² In 1998 and accordingly with national legislation, public schools were grouped on logics of territorial proximity and (therefore) community identity. Some schools were not possible to group, due to their specificities and/ or territorial isolation. These remained, therefore, as ungrouped schools.

¹³ PORDATA (Contemporary Portugal's database) / Foundation Francisco Manuel dos Santos (2021). Public schools in ECEC, primary and secondary education (1999-2019). Available at:

<https://www.pordata.pt/Portugal/Estabelecimentos-nos-ensinos+pr%c3%a9+escolar++b%c3%a1sico+e+secund%c3%a1rio+p%c3%bablico+total+e+por+n%c3%advel+de+ensino-1241> [accessed on 24/05/2021].

¹⁴ PORDATA (Contemporary Portugal's database) / Foundation Francisco Manuel dos Santos (2021). Private schools n ECEC, primary and secondary education (1999-2019). Available at:

<https://www.pordata.pt/Portugal/Estabelecimentos-nos-ensinos+pr%c3%a9+escolar++b%c3%a1sico+e+secund%c3%a1rio+privado+total+e+por+n%c3%advel+de+ensino-1242> [accessed on 24/05/2021].

¹⁵ Government of Portugal, "Ordinance on creating a national coordination team", 17/10/2018 (9726/2018). Available at: <https://dre.pt/home/-/dre/116696215/details/maximized> [accessed 08/06/2021].

duties), and working in a privileged *liaison* between the Government (AFC National Coordination and Regional Teams) and the schools.

AFC's sustainability and financing is ensured mainly by the state budget for the education sector. The National, Technical and Regional Commissions are composed of representatives of the bodies and services of the ministry of education¹⁶ and of 'specifically profiled' technicians coming from teachers' mobility. These also integrate the CFAE as liaison technicians. Consultancy close to the Minister of Education (and its Secretaries of State) is also financed by the state budget. In schools, as AFC allows saving formal curricular hours, teachers are compelled to use these extra hours to invest in direct (educative) and indirect (management) AFC related activities - as established in Order No. 10-B / 2018¹⁷.

Complementary funding is also being provided by European structural funds to ensure the works of the National Coordination Team, namely the support activities (and resources) necessary to launch, promote, supply and maintain AFC. These include:

- Graphical image creation and its harmonization and appliance for the AFC initiative
- Creation of an AFC website¹⁸ and production of materials and content
- Promotion of national and regional meetings
- Network meetings
- Proximity visits
- Monitoring and evaluation activities

One of the major innovations and positive aspects brought by the AFC initiative was the 'mandatory' articulation of the different services and bodies of the Ministry of Education, now present in the AFC National Coordination Committee:

- a) The Directorate-General for Education (DGE), which coordinates;
- b) The General Inspection of Education and Science (IGEC);
- c) The Directorate-General for School Administration (DGAE);
- d) The Directorate-General for School Establishments (DGEstE); and
- e) The National Agency for Qualification and Vocational Education, I. P., (ANQEP, I. P.),

This articulation allowed easing communication - between them and with schools - in both formal and informal ways, quickening the resolution of 'small' doubts and problems. Thereby, institutional and technical collaboration between the national, regional and local levels was highly improved.

¹⁶ Directorate-General of Education (2021). Organogram of DGE. Available at: <https://www.dge.mec.pt/organograma> [accessed 21/05/2021].

¹⁷ Ministry of Education, "Normative order on Rules for public schools of ECEC, primary and secondary education of the respective school year", 6 July 2018 (10-B/2018). Available at: <https://dre.pt/home/-/dre/115652972/details/maximized> [05/05/2021].

¹⁸ Directorate-General of Education (2021). *Autonomia e Flexibilidade Curricular* [Curriculum Flexibility and Autonomy]. Available at: <https://afc.dge.mec.pt/> [accessed 04/05/2021].

The AFC initiative is thought to be implemented as a reform project of the Portuguese education system, to be invigorated as an on-going process, and plans are to continue.

1.2.2. What are the main inputs of the initiative (resources – financial, human, administrative, etc – needed for the implementation of the initiative)?

The main inputs of the AFC initiative are:

- Financial: The national state budget, in combination with European structural funds and projects funds, ensures the necessary monetary support, in particular with regard on human resources (see next point);
- Human resources: AFC is coordinated on the macro level by governmental staff, mainly by the ministry of education and their executing organs (e.g. DGE); on meso level AFC is supported by so called “teachers in mobility” (teachers released from teaching duties and allocated elsewhere to provide support, e.g. in public professional training centers, that are another important pillar on the meso (and micro) level; on the micro level, AFC is implemented in daily school life by school staff from all levels (top board, teachers and assistants), as well by external stakeholders staff, e.g. local associations or community initiatives.
- Since AFC has become anchored in national law, governmental institutions, such as Directorate-General of Education (DGE) and related public organisations (e.g. public professional training centers for educational professional (Centros de Formação Associação de Escolas (CFAE)) at central and regional levels provide administrative and technical support to schools, e.g. in training and curricula redesign.

1.2.3. What are the main aims of the initiative? How was the idea of this initiative developed?

The main aim of the AFC initiative was to give schools more autonomy (and sense of belonging and responsibility) in re-designing themselves as transformative agents for the 21st century. The government’s core vision and proposal for schools was a shift from normalized/ standardized schooling with closed programs/ contents, to a personalized and co-constructed educational path with open proposals, that enable schools to critically reflect on the pedagogical intentionality of what they are doing, and decide how far they want to go.

This endeavour encompassed a vision and a clear invitation to schools to define their own identity, their particular position in the educational system, their own educational strategy and pedagogical approach: By operating through a curriculum in a more contextualized and ‘hands-on’ approach, i.e. in the local communities and including learning opportunities out of school and in real life, that would value continuous processes based on practical group work (projects), schools are challenged to strengthen their inter- and transdisciplinary collaboration (e.g. between teachers (from different disciplines) and local communities) and to foster engagement and participation, enabling a continuous approximation to a whole-school approach.

The initiative developed under the following sequential steps of implementation:

- A first experiment was conducted in the school year of 2016-2017, with 6 school clusters (comprehending 18 schools) invited to develop Pedagogical Innovation Pilot Projects (*PPIP- Projeto Piloto de Inovação Pedagógica*)¹⁹, allowing up to 100% autonomy in curriculum design;

- Later, in 2017-2018, a wider invitation was launched, reaching 226 participants (170 school clusters and non grouped schools from the public network and 56 schools from the private)(interviewee #3) to conduct a first experimental year of the AFC, thus called PAFC (Project of AFC), implemented in the first years of each cycle (1st, 5th, 7th and 10th grade);

- At the end of this experience, an evaluation report was published and widely disseminated, encouraging acceptance and further adhesion. Close consultancy to the ministry was provided by the Centre for Research and Intervention in Education (Faculty of Psychology and Educational Sciences, Universidade do Porto (CIEE FPCE UP)) (interviewees #3, #7 and #8), and a final report was produced²⁰. Furthermore, an independent perspective was also provided by an OECD review^{see 2};

- The initiative then evolved to a legal framework of compulsory adhesion that however allows schools to choose how far they would go with AFC implementation: from 0% to 25% of autonomous curriculum design (defined as the minimum range in the legislation), or - from 25% to 100% of autonomous curriculum design, committing to develop subsequent "innovation plans" (planos de inovação)^{see10} that would outline gradual AFC implementation, which was also recommended by the National Council of Education (CNE)(Art 13, DL 55/2018)^{see6};

- Finally, a three years implementation period occurred, covering the school years of 2018-2019, 2019-2020 and (now ending) 2020-2021. Another technical evaluation report was produced by CIEE FPCE UP, delivered in January and to be published this June 2021 (interviewees #3 and #7);

- The implementation formats adopted by schools varied: a) on the organizational level, AFC was implemented through the alteration of the school calendar (annual, school semester, school quarter) or through the inclusion of complementary subjects (STEM, social sciences, support for the study and integration of the arts); b) on the pedagogical level, AFC was introduced by inserting specific interdisciplinary thematic fields, so called Domains of Curricular Autonomy (*Domínios de Autonomia Curricular - DAC*²¹ that allows to develop interdisciplinary educational projects on certain topics (e.g. water).

¹⁹ Office of the State's Secretary of Education, "Order on authorization of the PPIP projects for 3 years", 03 May 2017 (3721/2017). Available at: <https://dre.pt/application/conteudo/106958832> [accessed 07/05/2021].

²⁰ Cosme, A. (2017). Projeto de Autonomia e Flexibilidade Curricular (PAFC): Estudo avaliativo da experiência pedagógica desenvolvida 2017/2018 ao abrigo do despacho nº 5708/2017 [Project on Curriculum Flexibility and Autonomy (PAFC): Assessment Study on the pedagogical experience developed in 2017/2018 under ordinance nr. 5708/2017. Available at: https://www.dge.mec.pt/sites/default/files/Curriculo/AFC/estudo_avaliativo_pafc_verseaoxl_logos.pdf [accessed 06/05/2021].

²¹ On AFC's official website DAC is described as follows: "A 'DAC' corresponds to an area of confluence of interdisciplinary work and curricular articulation that results from the exercise of flexibility management of the curriculum to which several disciplines are called. In this context, the planning, implementation and evaluation of teaching and learning proceed together,

1.2.4. What are the main activities/ outputs of the initiative?

AFC allows schools to choose the extent of their AFC implementation, as mentioned in 1.2.3. Schools that opted to go beyond the 25% curriculum flexibility, are obliged to develop so called “innovation plans” (plano de inovação) in which they outline how they redesign their curricula, i.e. how they manage the chosen percentage of a flexible curriculum. As a concrete output of the AFC legislation, more than 100 school clusters (~13% of the Portuguese school clusters)²² opted to go beyond the 25% of autonomous curriculum design and presented their innovation plans, which received official approval of the governmental authorities. In 2019/2020, 83 innovation plans²³ were approved, and in 2020/2021 112 innovation plans²⁴.

The main activities related to the AFC implementation consist of interdisciplinary educational projects, often in collaboration with the local communities. On the AFC website, these activities are divided into (i) curricular options²⁵, in which the interdisciplinary thematic fields - so called “DAC’s” (domains of curricula autonomy, see above) - appear to be the most frequently chosen option, as also stated by interviewees #16 and #17; (ii) educational and pedagogical dynamics²⁶; (iii) community projects²⁷; (iv) strategies and projects in citizenship education²⁸; (v) “perspective sharing”²⁹ - communication outputs in the form of reports or brochures on specific projects or topics elaborated by schools.

Another pillar of AFC implementation are activities related to training of educational staff. The Ministry of Education opted for a top-down strategy and gave priority to provide training to the directors of school clusters, considering this approach to be more pertinent and useful. Furthermore, in September 2019, started the

with learning also being mobilized for the disciplines of origin, which, among other aspects, will allow to assign classifications to each of the disciplines autonomously.”, Available at <https://afc.dge.mec.pt/apresentacao/faq> [accessed 24/05/2021].

²² Interview with consultant to DGE (#7), Lisbon (online), 17/05/2021.

²³ Government of Portugal, Approved innovation plans 2019/2020, based on “Ordinance on Innovation Plans”, 11/06/2019 (181/2019). Available at https://www.dge.mec.pt/sites/default/files/planos_de_inovacao_2019_2020.pdf [accessed 15/05/2021].

²⁴ Government of Portugal, Approved innovation plans 2020/2021, based on “Ordinance on Innovation Plans”, 11/06/2019 (181/2019). Available at https://www.dge.mec.pt/sites/default/files/lista_das_uo_com_pi_aprovado_2020_2021.pdf [accessed 15/05/2021].

²⁵ Directorate-General of Education (2021). Autonomia e Flexibilidade Curricular [Curriculum Flexibility and Autonomy] – Curricular Options. Available at: <https://afc.dge.mec.pt/> [accessed 04/05/2021]. <https://afc.dge.mec.pt/praticas/opcoes-curriculares> [accessed 15/05/2021]

²⁶ Directorate-General of Education (2021). Autonomia e Flexibilidade Curricular [Curriculum Flexibility and Autonomy] – Educational and pedagogical dynamics. Available at <https://afc.dge.mec.pt/praticas/dinamicas-de-trabalho-e-praticas-pedagogicas> [accessed on 15/05/2021].

²⁷ Directorate-General of Education (2021). Autonomia e Flexibilidade Curricular [Curriculum Flexibility and Autonomy] – Community projects. Available at <https://afc.dge.mec.pt/praticas/projetos-compara-comunidade> [accessed 15/05/2021].

²⁸ Directorate-General of Education (2021). Autonomia e Flexibilidade Curricular [Curriculum Flexibility and Autonomy] – Citizenship Education. Available at <https://afc.dge.mec.pt/praticas/educacao-para-cidadania> [accessed 15/05/2021].

²⁹ Directorate-General of Education (2021). Autonomia e Flexibilidade Curricular [Curriculum Flexibility and Autonomy] – Perspective sharing. Available at <https://afc.dge.mec.pt/partilhadeolhares/> [15/05/2021].

project MAIA³⁰ that aims to provide continuous professional development through reflections on monitoring, follow-up and research in pedagogical assessment. In collaboration with the public professional training centers CFAE, this project promoted more than 170 training workshops since 2019, reaching a universe of more than 3000 teachers, in about 400 school clusters³¹. As a result of the training actions of the project MAIA^{see 30}, around 400 intervention projects were developed.

However, most interviewees and focus group participants underlined that the current approach to teacher training is insufficient and that more systemic professional development and updated contents are needed in the initial teacher training as well in the continuous training offers. As for the effective implementation of the AFC in schools, it is still very dependent on single efforts of highly motivated and dedicated teachers. As noted by interviewees from the Portuguese National Council of Education, as well as from the teachers from a school cluster in the metropolitan area of Lisbon and from the professional training centers (interviewees #4-6; #12-14; #16-17), the current situation of only a few teachers being actively engaged in AFC related activities is of great inequality and unfortunately still tolerated in the educational system.

The 4-year experience of implementing the AFC has led to the perception that the schools that go further are not the ones with the most resources, but those with the strongest leadership; they are not those that have more support, but those that have more autonomy and flexibility to design and manage their curricula (interview #1).

1.3. Transformation

1.3.1. To what extent does the initiative foster the whole-institution and holistic approach? Please consider how it fosters learning 'about', 'in', 'through' and 'for' environmental sustainability.³²

AFC is part of a very powerful political vision and structured framework towards whole-institution and holistic approach. This was stated by all participants in the interviews and in the focus group. However, the whole-school approach is not yet embedded in the Portuguese school culture. EES/ ESD may be an excellent driving force to push this approach forward and to develop more systems-thinking competency. AFC can be seen as a participatory instrument to forge transformation towards a more participatory and, eventually even sociocratic, governance of schools. According to the majority of the participants in this study, the key seems to be in transcribing the national vision to the local institutional context, which requires a high level of dialogue, critical reflection and collaboration between teachers and school staff, students, parents, and other agents of the broader school community.

³⁰ Directorate-General of Education (2021). *Autonomia e Flexibilidade Curricular [Curriculum Flexibility and Autonomy] – MAIA Project (Projeto MAIA - Projeto de Monitorização, Acompanhamento e Investigação em Avaliação Pedagógica)*. Available at: <https://afc.dge.mec.pt/projeto-maia-introducao> [15/05/2021].

³¹ <https://afc.dge.mec.pt/projeto-maia/documentos-do-projeto>

³² These four concepts refer to the following: a) *about* – content focused; b) *in* – in the environment being studied; c) *through* – setting the 'culture', e.g., learning through peace by creating peaceful classrooms, care, whole school approach with values, etc.; d) *for* – action learning, critical thinking, futures thinking, systems thinking.

Schools that successfully implemented AFC, like the school cluster of Azeitão (Lisbon metropolitan area) that participated in this study, apply project-based learning in forms of the "DACs" (Domains of curricula autonomy - specific interdisciplinary thematic fields, see above) and in the form of their Citizenship Education Strategy.

At the school cluster of Azeitão, Citizenship Education is mandatory and approached in an inter- and transdisciplinary manner. The school educational project "*Educating in citizenship by linking fields of knowledge [S@bERES³³]*" is the key framework for this vision in which diverse disciplinary fields of knowledge are combined with active and participatory engagement of students and staff: The school developed workshops called "Knowledge(s) without borders" [*S@bERES sem fronteiras*], held debates and assemblies, encouraged supervised autonomous work and promoted collaboration with other projects (e.g., with the eco-school project "The Ocean Starts Here") (Interviewees #13-15).

Furthermore, the school cluster Azeitão has put great focus on EES, from the start, making the most out of the proximity to the Arrábida Natural Park that offers excellent opportunities for place-based learning, as the park director explains:

"The Arrábida Natural Park is a privileged scenario to develop land art, geography and mathematics, awakening students to the conservation of our land. It stimulates us to learn to preserve what is close to us. It gives our students a good foundation for learning, as they experience: I learn from my context, from the environment around me [place-based learning]³⁴."

The following examples can be seen as examples for learning 'about', 'in', 'through' and 'for' sustainability, and belong to the work on EES within AFC implementation at the school cluster Azeitão:

- At primary school level, they created a curricular area within the Complementary Offer (OC) called "Development, Environment and Sustainability" (DAS)³⁵. The themes promote interdisciplinarity and cover e.g. Sustainable Development, Biodiversity, Climate Change and Art. The school follows the idea of a "school without walls" in order to provide contextualized and meaningful learning (interviewees #12-15). Thereby, citizenship, teamwork, cooperation between children and developing the capacity for sociability and environmental responsibility are fostered. Various activities relate to environmental issues³⁶, like the vegetable gardens (interviewees #13-15).
- At other school levels (lower and upper secondary), they promote students' activities in the local natural environment, taking the students to the outdoors and exploring environmental aspects in the scope of different subjects (interviewees #16 and #17). Concrete examples are: (i) a partnership project with the local cooperative *Ocean Alive*³⁷ on marine prairies, and (ii) the *Science in our Serra-Project*, in which science classes from different years, coordinated by school teachers and park biologists, explore the local Alambre Natural Park. Today, the project is a space for the development of specific

³³ School Cluster Azeitão (2019). Educational Project. Available at:

http://site.aveazeitao.pt/images/PDF/PE_AE_Azeitao_2019_2022.pdf [accessed on 16/05/2021].

³⁴ Report tv: Available at:

<https://tvi24.iol.pt/videos/sociedade/estas-aulas-de-ciencias-dao-se-na-serra-da-arrabida/581a24ae0cf277d677a4c269?jwsourc=cl>

³⁵ School Cluster Azeitão (2019). Innovation Plans 2019-2022 (Plano de Inovação 2019-2022. Autonomia e Flexibilidade Curricular). Available at:

http://site.aveazeitao.pt/images/PDF/Plano_Inovacao_AE_AZEITAO_2019_07_29_enviado_corrigido.pdf [accessed 16/05/2021]-

³⁶ School Cluster Azeitão (2020). Evaluation of school cluster activities Plan 2020/2021 - 1st semester.

Available at: http://site.aveazeitao.pt/images/PDF/PAA_2020_2021_AVAL_1_SEMESTRE_vf.pdf

³⁷ No planet B Project - Ocean Alive (2021). "O Oceano dá bom clima". Available at: <https://pt.noplanetb.net/project/o-oceano-da-bom-clima/> [accessed 16/05/2021].

environmental role-plays (learning scenarios³⁸), involving not only the science teachers but also those from other disciplines, conducting these activities together as practical outdoor onsite learning. In this project, financial support was assured, first through crowdfunding, then through the local authority.

Other examples for holistic learning approaches within AFC were provided by interviewees #2 and #4: (i) the sustainability initiative "It's with you - it's with all [ECONTIGO ECOMTODOS]"³⁹ from several governmental entities in order to promote the forest among young people, carried out on World Forest Day in 100 Portuguese schools; (ii) the project "Planting a Million Trees", carried out within a DAC; and (iii) the Regional Curriculum of Azores Islands, considered to be outstanding in Europe.

Interviewees from the Portuguese Council for Education (CNE) (#4-6) highlight AFC's contribution to fostering EES by promoting a certain perspective of seeing the world as our home, as well as the school as a place to connect with the world, which can be regarded as a systemic (ecosystemic) perspective, closely linked to the vision and concept of the whole-school. This aspect is strongly reinforced in the OECD's 2018 report "Future of Education and Skills: Education 2030", namely in the "design principles for moving toward an eco-systemic change", stating that "engaging with school will be the first step to engage with the world"⁴⁰.

Interviewees from CNE also refer to the importance of the development of 'communities of practice', involving the collaboration of different educational agents in the analysis of problems, difficulties and in the development and evaluation of solution proposals: In their opinion, the challenge is to evolve into 'communities of practice' in which the school is or can be seen as a 'living and plural organism' that develops in an integral way.

Finally, the legislation about the Inclusive School^{see 8}, that provides the legal basis for a school that not only includes everyone but promotes citizenship values, is undoubtedly the document that further deepens the vision and concept of the whole-school. Therefore, the inclusive school also strengthens the links between AFC and EES: since diversity is an educational asset, schools are being compelled to do differently (accordingly with their own reality and specificities - human, territorial and others).

1.3.2. To what extent does the initiative impact students' knowledge, attitudes and behaviours and foster action competences?

In this case study development, it was not possible to conduct interviews with students. However, the AFC initiative itself promoted a feedback event in 2019⁴¹ where four students from different schools and ages/educational levels (lower and upper secondary) participated in a podium discussion. This discussion shed some light on students' perceptions on how AFC is impacting students' knowledge, attitudes and behaviours. Being aware of the fact that these students were selected for having a positive perspective, the moderator - a

³⁸ A learning scenario is understood as a hypothetical teaching-learning situation (purely imagined or with real straits) composed of a set of elements. Each scenario must describe (i) the context in which the learning takes place, (ii) the environment in which it takes place and which is conditioned by factors related to the area / domain of knowledge, (iii) the roles played by the different agents or actors (and for their objectives), organized in a story / narrative. (<http://itelab.ie.ulisboa.pt/tel/gbook/contextualizacao/>)

³⁹ <http://florestacomfuturo.pt/>

⁴⁰ OECD (2018). The future of education and skills: 2030. Available at [https://www.oecd.org/education/2030-project/about/documents/E2030%20Position%20Paper%20\(05.04.2018\).pdf](https://www.oecd.org/education/2030-project/about/documents/E2030%20Position%20Paper%20(05.04.2018).pdf) [accessed 25/05/2021].

⁴¹ Available at: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=hW7KpUMEtC0&t=5s>

journalist highly familiar with school realities - asked questions in a very open and frank way, and the students' answers seemed honest and authentic, also identifying less positive aspects. These students referred to the positive contribution that AFC has brought to schools in general, namely fostering students' involvement in active learning through projects and less teacher-centered learning. These projects offered an integrated approach to different curricular areas, anchored in real-world problems, and strengthened diverse transversal competences, such as collaborative skills, self and group responsibility, communication and decision-making based on negotiation and group consensus, critical use of information and knowledge, data collection, analysis and interpretation, and critical reflection on possible solutions. The most relevant aspect, in our perspective, was the reflective capacity students demonstrated in this discussion, and also their consciousness developed about citizenship education: Key areas are being worked through the process itself and students consider sustainability related questions most interesting and relevant to study and deepen in these projects, as this type of questions relate to the most important - and far from solved - problems of the actuality.

Several interviewees see AFC's impact on students' knowledge, attitudes and behaviours in fostering action competence, as AFC promotes permeability between disciplines and knowledge sharing. However, university researchers who are in close consultancy to the government in AFC and education for sustainability (interviewees #7 and #8) state that there is still a giant leap to be made: to establish sustainability and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) as a core reference and value framework in all schools, as such a reference would shape the schools' educational projects and curricula. In their opinion, schools should respond to the question: "How is our school going to address and respond to each of these goals (SDG) - and how is the curriculum of each discipline and learning domain going to contribute to achieve them; and how are this learning and knowledge acquisition going to be ensured amongst our students, in order that they are able to understand the underlying problems and find the necessary solutions?"(interviewee #7)⁴²

1.3.3. What are the main results of the initiative? To what extent has the initiative been successful and effective in bringing about transformative change in the area of education for sustainability?⁴³

The initiative results are expressed in terms of the main achievements of AFC' development and implementation in three stages, including: the first small pilot on innovation plans, in 2016-2017 (PPIP^{see 18}); the larger experience on AFC, in 2017-2018 (PAFC); and the three years' experience on AFC:

1. In the first stage of PPIP (pedagogic innovation pilot-project) (see 1.2.3), its evaluation report⁴⁴ concluded that, in participating school clusters, dropout rates have fallen to a residual level, with upward trends in students' academic results. These positive results express the higher involvement and motivation of students (and teachers) to learn (and teach) collaboratively, developing a spirit of community belonging among peers. This encompasses the transformative change needed in shifting

⁴² Interview with university professor and consultant to DGE (#7). Lisbon (online), 17/05/2021.

⁴³ The indicators for transformative change vary. The measurement of transformative change can span from quantitative indicators, i.e. the amount of people involved/engaged as well as the amount of outputs produced; to less tangible indicators, such as how a) progressive (in a normative sense), b) systemic (addressing various factors simultaneously and in an interrelated way), and c) long term (cannot be easily reversed in the short term) an initiative is.

⁴⁴ Costa, E. & Almeida, M. (2019). IE-Estudo de avaliação do Projeto-Piloto de Inovação Pedagógica, Universidade de Lisboa. Available at: https://www.dge.mec.pt/sites/default/files/Curriculo/AFC/relatorio_de_avaliacao_externa_do_ppip.pdf [accessed 07/06/2021].

to an interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary view of the world - in which sustainability is at the core. These results were key to the advance of a legal framework to offer an open possibility to all schools to implement their innovation plans, reaching up to 100% curricular autonomy and flexibility^{see18}.

2. In the AFC Pilot-Project stage (PAFC), its evaluation report (and interviews with representatives from DGE(#1-3) as well as from Universidade do Porto (#7-9),) led to conclude that this project was of huge importance, as it allowed schools that were already on the AFC path to 'gain wings and fly', overcoming the previous legal constraints, having not only an opportunity to conduct an effective change, but also a formal framework to support it.

From the 200 school clusters that accepted the challenge, around 180 completed the PAFC period fully. Some schools dropped out for not having the right conditions. Achievements included⁴⁵: (1) more innovation in curriculum management, pedagogical and assessment practices; (2) more time (for teachers) to collaborate and articulate their work; (3) more time of teachers with students (as they assumed more disciplines within curricular domains, diminishing the number of teachers per school, but increasing knowledge of their population - students needs, desires, potentialities - thus better informing values and competencies to be developed and essential learning to be conveyed); (4) less bureaucracy (as collaboration and articulation increased - and as students' difficulties and needs were better understood and solved, avoiding disciplinary (and other) formal procedures; (5) more connection with local communities through partnerships, with synergies and gains in curriculum/ teachers' teaching hours and students' time in classes, as some classes were given outside the school and/ or by invited guests from the community.

PAFC's general idea, of (re)designing schools' mission in accordance with the reality of their territories, fostered an 'emancipated territorial governance', embracing diversity as an asset and thus smoothing inequalities. The reflection on "what is school for?" - much conveyed through citizenship education (still controversial in terms of its necessity as a discipline, *versus* integration in all disciplines) - may finally and adequately be addressed.

Finally, the official results of the 'post-legislation' phase of AFC implementation (2018-2019 to 2020-2021), are not yet public (see 1.2.3), but the contributions from the 7 interviews and 1 focus group session, allow the following conclusions:

- (a) Results may not be so positive, as now all schools entered the AFC implementation phase and are at different paces and diverse contextual conditions;
- (b) The pandemic due to COVID-19 has decelerated AFC implementation, but its impacts were lower once AFC had already led to the introduction of more collaborative and integrated practices amongst teachers and with students;
- (c) Government's support in training (especially of top leaderships) and sharing of practices (amongst teachers) fostered the development of intermediate leaderships (this happened e.g. in the school cluster of Azeitão (#12);
- (d) In the process of AFC evaluation, all involved entities collaborated with each other, which is AFC's own 'seal' (and objective, namely the collaboration between the professional training centers (CFAE) and higher education institutions, but also between governmental bodies;

⁴⁵ Cosme, A. (2017). Projeto de Autonomia e Flexibilidade Curricular (PAFC): Estudo avaliativo da experiência pedagógica desenvolvida 2017/2018 ao abrigo do despacho nº 5708/2017 [Project on Curriculum Flexibility and Autonomy (PAFC): Assessment Study on the pedagogical experience developed in 2017/2018 under ordinance nr. 5708/2017. Available at: https://www.dge.mec.pt/sites/default/files/Curriculo/AFC/estudo_avaliativo_pafc_versaoxl_logos.pdf [accessed 06/05/2021].

- (e) AFC was not adopted by more conservative high schools (possible reasons can be a stronger attachment to formal mechanisms of summative evaluation and less socio-economic diversity (higher representation of students from social elites) that reflect on different driving forces for AFC implementation.

In conclusion, AFC brings about transformative change in the area of education for sustainability, especially in schools already aligned with such a vision and valuing endogenous resources of their territories and communities. This on-going transformative change, as referred to by a representative from CNE (interview #2), calls for a deep reflection on what we need and want to learn, that should be transcribed to the school dimension. The Government has already been working on such questions within the 'National Skills Strategy'⁴⁶. This strategy recommends the development of relevant content (also in adult education), achieved through the expansion of collaborative offers between different training agents and stakeholders of the local communities.

Education for Sustainable Development seems to be key to achieve a transformative change in the 21st century, both as a global planetary ethic and as an individual praxis of and for the 'commons'. The whole-institution approach seems to be key to allow schools to walk towards that goal. However, it is still necessary to harmonize and unify its concept, language, discourse and content, so that school practices may be embedded with the needed consistency to attain this systemic view.

1.3.4. Based on available evidence (desk research and interviews) and expert assessment, what were the enablers and barriers for the implementation, mainstreaming and sustainability of the initiative? Are there any examples/indications on how these challenges and barriers have been addressed or are planned to be addressed?

The identified essential enablers and barriers for AFC (and within it, EES) implementation, mainstreaming and sustainability, are the following:

<p><u>Enablers:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - SDG as driving force (SDG 4 in particular) to mainstream ESD in Portugal. - "EDS for 2030: a Roadmap" (UNESCO) as an opportunity to put EES at the core. - Government training strategy in AFC and information technology (IT) to empower leaders and teachers. - Project funding at national (ENEA) and European (Structural Funds) levels. 	<p><u>Barriers:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - AFC dissolution 'in time' (losing novelty) - due to pandemic and newer things. - Lack of persistence and resistance to change from school leaders and teachers. - 'Old school' teachers and persistence in following strict programs and manuals. - Pandemic (political priorities and practical obstacles). - Lack of digital resources and knowledge and use of IT.
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⁴⁶ OECD, 2018. Skills Studies. Skills Strategy Implementation Guidance for Portugal Strengthening the Adult-Learning System. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264298705-en> [accessed 17/05/2021]

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Holistic and Whole-School Approach as a key concept with growing acceptance. - Community engagement as key growing practice (especially at local level) - Government strategy on 'Hearing the Students' as youth empowerment opportunity. - Government strategy on Digital Knowledge (and tools) as an accelerator of EES. - Participatory governance mechanisms as disseminators of good practices. - School empowerment and proactive attitude to seek resources (partners, volunteers, funds). - Availability of parents to get involved (especially after the pandemic experience). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Unrecognized, tired, aged (and low paid) professional class of teachers. - Competition and attempt to discredit achievements due to differences in quality and availability of own resources. - Lack / absence of support (AFC structures failure due to tiredness, unavailability and/ or lack of funding). - Lack of a EES/ ESD specific/ privileged interlocutor. - Lack (or different levels) of parental involvement.
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In conclusion to this list, it seems clear that, to ensure AFC success, it will be necessary to (i) allocate resources - human, technical, scientific, training - that may bring to all schools the necessary skills - strong top leadership (and cooperative intermediate leaderships); (ii) adequate capacity building (e.g. in collaborative, participatory methodologies and practices, as well as in less common knowledge areas, namely of EES); (iii) efficiency in operationalization (taking risks in the appropriation of the AFC framework to adapt and respond to each school's real needs and potentials, e.g., by exploring 'hidden' resources); and (iv) follow-up evaluation that can strengthen the school capacity to set goals and targets, reflect on results, change strategies and adapt and evolve in a continuous way.

1.3.5. If it was initially a local/ regional initiative, has it become mainstream nationally? Are there delivery mechanisms already within the education system that would make it possible to introduce this practice at the national level, and if so, what are they?

This is a national initiative directed to all schools within compulsory education. Furthermore, it could be extended to ECEC and adapted to higher education (in ECEC, some schools are already following AFC). Furthermore, it could evolve to better support schools in attaining higher curricular autonomy and flexibility. Ideally, all schools could be innovative schools and elaborate their own innovation plans, as foreseen in AFC.

Government is prioritizing training and capacity building of top leadership - as top leaders are seen as the core drivers to induce motivation and change in their institutions - and also in teachers' meetings, sharing of practices, and exchange of knowledge and experiences.

Collaboration and concerted action between ministries and governmental bodies is also stimulating information, initiatives, projects, partners and operative funding mechanisms that can help to encourage schools to take risks, affirm themselves and be more proactive in managing their institutions through curriculum development outside the school, i.e. beyond the outer walls of the school and embed parts of their curriculum in the community.

1.3.6. What are the main strengths and weaknesses of the initiative?⁴⁷

The identified essential strengths and weaknesses of AFC are the following:

<u>Strengths:</u>	<u>Weaknesses:</u>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Political vision and will - and governance stability. - Convergence between educational policies and executive entities. - Support framework (strategy, agents, channels and mechanisms - in planning, implementing, monitoring and evaluating). - Strong top leaderships - government support with training and capacity-building. - Teachers' collaboration and sharing, through formal and informal means, at local, regional and national levels. - Collaborative and participatory pedagogies and pedagogical practices. - Self and external assessment and evaluation promoted by government and partnerships (with universities). - Space for schools' self-determination. - Whole-School and holistic approach, inter and transdisciplinary work. - Community engagement and local partners' involvement through projects. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Too liberal (schools get lost in such freedom; in some schools this is the case, for they are not prepared in terms of capacity building to deal with AFC) - Difference between formal and practical/ effective commitment. - Still high dependence on schools' endogenous resources to strive (socioeconomic context; quality of infrastructures; leaderships; etc). - Lack of human/ technical and financial resources to capacitate, plan, implement, monitor, assess and evaluate. - Teachers' general level of exhaustion (called to be super heroes). - Lack of training/ professional development amongst teachers - and weak intermediate leaderships (within the school). - Lack of common view and alignment of concepts, language/ discourse and contents. - ESD and SDG are still more present in natural sciences related curricula than in other disciplines. -Lack of school autonomy in (financial) management.

⁴⁷ Examples of strengths: easily transferable to other national contexts, requires little funding for scaling up, fosters the whole-institution approach, etc. Examples of weaknesses: contextually bound to a specific country/region, difficult to implement without extensive funding, difficult to replicate due to the voluntary nature of actors fostering the initiative, etc.

	- Schools' difficulty in being more open to their context (community, families, associations, companies, local authorities).
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1.3.7. How does the national context in your country impact the effectiveness and sustainability of the initiative?

Portugal is facing a period of political stability, namely in education, with general high acceptance of this new educational policy - although several concerns remain -, what is much due to the involvement of the different stakeholders since the beginning.

The pandemic interrupted many of the AFC activities and urged the government and schools to focus on other priorities than the AFC implementation - and within it, EES. However, the pandemic highlighted precisely the importance of the ecological and environmental dimension of human development on Earth, and, thus, EES gained even more strength and consensus on its core role to shift the current paradigm towards the needed transformational change.

1.3.8. How could the initiative be improved? What were the main challenges that had to be overcome to proceed with the initiative? Please elaborate on both managerial (e.g., how to ensure funding) and substantial (e.g., how to ensure positive impact) challenges. What were the main opportunities/ solutions that allowed to overcome these challenges?

One of the most important challenges that had to be overcome in implementing AFC was ensuring schools' effective involvement and active participation. To achieve this, capacity building and training of top leaders was essential. However, to be fully successful, all teachers (and other staff - and broadly, the whole education community) should be "upcycled" into AFC and EES. Practically, all participants in this study referred to the effective necessity to redesign and develop strong initial training of teachers, that integrates the holistic perspective and whole-institution approach, and also leadership skills based on democratic governance, to accelerate their potential as schools' change makers. In this sense, also higher education institutions are required to enter more boldly in reformulation of future teachers' studies. Within the focus group, improving initial and continuous professional development of educational staff was one of the most often mentioned measures to scale up AFC.

Another aspect is evaluation. AFC is based on schools' ability to develop their own assessment tools. Setting objectives, goals and targets - and measuring progress through indicators - is essential as a result of reflection, decision, action, observation and (again) reflection, in a spiral towards continuous improvement. The vast majority of schools still do not have embedded this managerial culture and scientific approach, that can be provided in an easier way, if schools are in close partnership with e.g. universities. This is / could be a win-win relation, as stated by interviewees #7 and #12, where the latter referred that such relationship already exists, reinforcing that a way to redesign initial teachers' training are universities working close with schools in order to be in close contact with social realities and to develop mutual and reciprocal learning opportunities for

schools and universities likewise. Another way to improve evaluation practices is through schools' close relation with training centers (interviewee #16), who can provide tools to support this strategic managerial and pedagogical embedding of AFC and EES into the school culture.

1.3.9. Do you know if the initiative has been transferred to other regions outside your country? If so, is there evidence on its usefulness for other contexts or how it can be adopted successfully to other local contexts? What, if any, are the limitations to transferability of the initiative? How can they be overcome?

AFC is a national initiative that has its own historical background and political and sociocultural context, so it cannot be simply transferred to different contexts. However, in accordance with participants' statements and our personal assessment, it is possible to adapt and transfer AFC's implementation steps (described in 1.2.3), as well as its managerial and educational/ pedagogical practices to other European countries.

Moreover - and more importantly - AFC seems to be really working as a launching pad for EES, and if the combined synergies of its two underlying policies - education policy and sustainable development policy - are further developed and supported - this can surely bring more light and insights on what can be 'the way ahead', not only for Portugal, but also to other EU countries.

1.4. Conclusion

1.4.1. Please reflect on the key lessons that can be derived from the implementation of the initiative that could be valuable for other country contexts or education levels.

The key lessons of the AFC development and implementation process are:

- (1) As stated above, one of the major innovations and positive aspects brought by the AFC initiative was the 'mandatory' articulation of the different governmental entities and other related public institutions, allowing a more effective communication between these institutions and between them and the schools, in both formal and informal ways. Thereby, institutional and technical collaboration between the national, regional and local levels was highly improved.
- (2) The government's core vision and proposal for schools was a shift from normalized/ standardized schooling with closed programs/ contents, to a personalized and co-constructed educational path with open proposals, that enable schools to critically reflect on the pedagogical intentionality of what they are doing, and decide how far they want to go. This approach allowed schools to define their own identity, providing opportunities and choices to execute the curricula redesign.
- (3) The 4-year experience of implementing the AFC has led to the perception that the schools that go further are those with the strongest leadership and that have more autonomy and flexibility to design and manage their curricula. However, the government must not neglect its commitment

and responsibility in providing technical support to schools during the AFC implementation phase, assuring that AFC becomes a framework for all, not leaving schools at a slower pace behind. In this regard, especially parents - and key agents from the local community - should be called to participate and be involved, for they are part of the transformative process.

- (4) Adequate capacity building (e.g. in collaborative and participatory methodologies and practices) and training are key for transformative change. As mentioned above, all participants in this study referred to the effective necessity to redesign and develop strong initial training of teachers, that integrates the holistic perspective and whole-institution approach, and also leadership skills based on democratic governance, to accelerate their potential as schools' change makers. In this sense, also higher education institutions are required to enter more boldly in the reformulation of future teachers' studies. Improving initial and continuous professional development of educational staff can be regarded as a prerequisite for mainstreaming sustainability-oriented educational practices.

1.4.2. Please provide any additional comments, important information and conclusions to further explain the context in which the selected initiative operates and makes it successful.

To make AFC a winner in the long run, all stakeholders (government, educational institutions, schools, school leaders and teachers, parents/ families, local authorities, companies, ONG) must come together and fully open up to the last barrier that holds education's transformation change: the recognition that focus must be on students, once students are the ones who really want a relevant education that prepares them for the pressing questions and complex problems of today and tomorrow. Students are going through life, education and schooling, where they acquire new values, principles, awareness and a large variety of fields of learning. Students may be better equipped than us adults for the global challenges. So, we all should listen to students very carefully. Only this idea of paying attention and listening is an essential shift in the predisposition to learn, including us in the group of lifelong learners, and making space for a type of learning and respectful relationship where the master becomes the pupil and the pupil becomes the master.

Unfortunately, the expert team could not further develop this last item, as there was no extra time to further deepen the reflection and collectively mature the findings of the desk research, the 7 interviews and the 1 focus group dynamic, due to the pressing time constraints in which this study needed to be developed.

○ ANNEX I – Key Acronyms

Acronyms:

ABAE - *Associação Bandeira Azul da Europa*

AE- School clusters (*Agrupamentos de Escolas*)

AFC - Curriculum Flexibility and Autonomy (*Autonomia e Flexibilidade Curricular*)

CIEE FPCE UP - Centre for Research and Intervention in Education, Faculty of Psychology and Educational Sciences, Universidade do Porto

CONFAP- *Confederação Nacional das Associações de Pais*

CFAE- Training centers for educational professionals (*Centros de Formação de Associação de Escola*)

CNE- National Education Council

DGE - Directorate-General for Education

EC – Citizenship Education

ENA - Non grouped schools (*Escolas Não Agrupadas*)

ESD – Education for Sustainable Development

EES – Education for Environmental Sustainability

ENEA - National Environmental Education Strategy

ENEC - National Strategy for Citizenship Education

MAIA- Monitoring, supervision and research in pedagogical assessment project (*Monitorização, Acompanhamento e Investigação em Avaliação Pedagógica*)

SDG - Sustainable Development Goals

PAFC - Project of Curriculum Flexibility and Autonomy (Projeto de Autonomia e Flexibilidade Curricular)

PIIP - Pedagogical Innovation Pilot Projects (*Projeto Piloto de Inovação Pedagógica*)

ANNEX II - Tables

Annex: Table A1 Sample - Participants profile (anonymized)

#	I*	FG**	affiliation (anonymised where necessary)	Professional role	Gen.	Interviewer / moderator***	Date
1	no	FG	DGE - Direção Geral de Educação (General Directorate of Education; executing organ of the Ministry of Education to implement, monitor and evaluate educational policies)	leading representative	f	AS/RF/AD	19/05/2021
2	I	no		team leader in Citizenship Education	m	RF	17/05/2021
3	I	no		team leader in Curriculum Development	f	RF	17/05/2021
4	I	no	Portuguese Educational Council (CNE), an independent advisory body on educational matters	leading representative	m	RF	18/05/2021
5	I	no		Counselor	m	RF	18/05/2021
6	I	no		technical-scientific advisor	m	RF	18/05/2021
7	I	no	Universidade do Porto	assistant professor in educational sciences / consultant to DGE	f	RF	17/05/2021
8	I	no		Researcher (Educational Sciences)	f	RF	17/05/2021
9	I	no		Researcher (Educational Sciences)	f	RF	20/05/2021
10	no	FG	Institute of Education, Universidade de Lisboa	Associate Professor (Educational Sciences)	m	AS/RF/AD	19/05/2021
11	no	FG	ABAE (Portuguese association representing Eco-Schools)	leading representative	f	AS/RF/AD	19/05/2021
12	I	FG	School cluster in the region of Setúbal (metropolitan area of Lisbon)	Director of the school cluster	f	AS (I) + AS/RF/AD (FG)	13/05/2021 (FG 19/05/21)
13	I	no		Primary school teacher (1st-4th grade)	f	AS	14/05/2021
14	I	FG		Lower secondary school teacher (5th-6th grade)	f	AS (I) + AS/RF/AD (FG)	14/05/2021 (FG 19/05/21)
15	I	no		Lower secondary school teacher (7th-9th grade)	f	AS	14/05/2021
16	I	FG	public professional training center for educational professionals	leading representative	m	AS (I) + AS/RF/AD (FG)	12/05/2021 (FG 19/05/21)
17	I	no		teacher released from teaching to accompany the AFC	m	AS	12/05/2021
18	no	FG	CONFAP - national confederation of parental associations in Portugal	leading representative	m	AS/RF/AD	19/05/2021
	14	7			f	10	
	(I)	(FG)			m	8	

Legend: *I = Interview; **FG = Focus Group; *** AS = Alexandra Silva, RF = Rita Fouto, AD = Antje Disterheft

Table A2 - List of interviews by affiliation

Int.	affiliation (anonymised where necessary)	Participants	Gen	Researcher	Date
I1	DGE - Direção Geral de Educação (General Directorate of Education; executing organ of the Ministry of Education to implement, monitor and evaluate educational policies)	Team leader in Citizenship Education	m	RF	17/05/2021
		Team leader in Curriculum Development	f	RF	17/05/2021
I2	Portuguese Educational Council (CNE), an independent advisory body on educational matters	Leading representative	m	RF	18/05/2021
		Counselor	m	RF	18/05/2021
		Technical-scientific advisor	m	RF	18/05/2021
I3	Universidade do Porto	Assistant professor in educational sciences / consultant to DGE	f	RF	17/05/2021
		Researcher (Educational Sciences)	f	RF	17/05/2021
I4	Universidade do Porto	Researcher (Educational Sciences)	f	RF	20/05/2021
I5	School cluster in the region of Setúbal (metropolitan area of Lisbon)	Director of the school cluster	f	AS	13/05/2021
I6	School cluster in the region of Setúbal (metropolitan area of Lisbon)	Primary school teacher (1st-4th grade)	f	AS	14/05/2021
		Lower secondary school teacher (5th-6th grade)	f	AS	14/05/2021
		Lower secondary school teacher (7th-9th grade)	f	AS	14/05/2021
I7	Public professional training center for educational professionals	leading representative	m	AS	12/05/2021
		teacher released from teaching to accompany the AFC	m	AS	12/05/2021

Total interviews: 7; total female participants: 8, total male participants: 6

Table A3 - Focus group composition

(Focus group held on 19/05/2021, online via zoom, facilitated by AS, RF and AD)

#	Professional role	Affiliation (anonymised where necessary)	Gender
FG1	Leading representative	DGE - Direção Geral de Educação (General Directorate of Education; executing organ of the Ministry of Education to implement, monitor and evaluate educational policies)	f
FG2	Associate Professor (Educational Sciences)	Institute of Education, Universidade de Lisboa	m
FG3	Leading representative	ABAE (Portuguese association representing Eco-Schools)	f
FG4	Director of the school cluster	School cluster in the region of Setúbal (metropolitan area of Lisbon)	f
FG5	Lower secondary school teacher (5th-6th grade)	School cluster in the region of Setúbal (metropolitan area of Lisbon)	f
FG6	Leading representative	public professional training center for educational professionals	m
FG7	Leading representative	CONFAP - national confederation of parental associations in Portugal	m

Total participants: 7, total female participants: 4; total male participants: 3

ANNEX III - Interview template for interview with DGE

Autonomia e Flexibilidade Curricular - Caso de Estudo Português no âmbito do Estudo Europeu sobre a Educação para a Sustentabilidade Ambiental

Guião de perguntas

Perguntas para a Direção-Geral da Educação (DGE) no âmbito da iniciativa governamental da Autonomia e Flexibilidade Curricular (AFC)

Este estudo decorre a pedido da Comissão Europeia e é liderado pelo centro de investigação europeu [PPMI](#). O objetivo central deste estudo é investigar as políticas e abordagens nacionais e institucionais da Educação para a Sustentabilidade Ambiental (EES) nos 27 Estados-membros da União Europeia.

A iniciativa da Autonomia e Flexibilidade Curricular (AFC) foi selecionada como um de cinco casos de estudo que ajudarão a aprofundar o estudo europeu. Pode encontrar mais informações sobre o estudo e as diferentes fases [aqui](#).

Objetivos da entrevista:

(i) Conhecer mais aprofundadamente a iniciativa governamental da AFC, quer ao nível da sua génese e historial de implementação, quer ao nível da situação atual e perspetivas futuras;

(ii) Entender melhor como, do ponto de vista da DGE, a AFC contribui e pode contribuir para a Educação para a Sustentabilidade Ambiental (EES), quer no âmbito da Estratégia de Educação para a Cidadania quer noutros âmbitos.

Garantia de privacidade e proteção de dados

Muito obrigado pela sua disponibilidade para participar neste estudo. Garantimos o anonimato de todos os dados recolhidos e a observação de todas as normas de privacidade e de proteção de dados definidas pela Comissão Europeia. Os dados serão eliminados no fim do estudo. Agradecemos a assinatura da Declaração de Privacidade que autoriza a sua participação neste estudo.

Perguntas:

1. Historial e enquadramento

1.1 Qual foi a força motriz para o surgimento da AFC em Portugal? Que necessidades/lacunas veio colmatar?

1.2 Qual foi e tem sido o papel da DGE nesta iniciativa?

1.3 De que forma a DGE considera que a AFC exprime - e tem contribuído para concretizar - a visão, estratégia e objetivos da política educativa nacional?

2. Implementação nas escolas

2.1 Como tem sido operacionalizada a implementação da AFC nas escolas?

2.1.1 Que agentes têm sido envolvidos?

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- 2.1.2 Que opções de desenho/concepção têm sido (mais comumente) adotadas?
- 2.1.3 Como tem sido garantido o financiamento e a sustentabilidade da iniciativa?
- 2.1.4 Que estratégias (e passos) têm sido seguidos na sua implementação?
- 2.1.5 Como tem decorrido o acompanhamento?
- 2.1.6 Como tem sido efetuada a monitorização e avaliação?
- 2.2 Que resultados têm sido obtidos ao longo deste período de implementação?

3. AFC e EES (Educação para a Sustentabilidade Ambiental)

Tendo em conta o período de implementação decorrido até aqui, na perspetiva da DGE...

- 3.1 Até que ponto é que a AFC tem contribuído para uma visão e abordagem holística das instituições educativas (ver a escola *'como um todo'* - abordagem da escola integral, *whole-school-approach*)?
- 3.2 Até que ponto a AFC promove a aprendizagem *"sobre"*, *"em"*, *"através"* e *"para"* a cidadania e sustentabilidade¹? Pode dar algum exemplo?
- 3.3 Quais os impactos da AFC nos conhecimentos, atitudes e comportamentos dos alunos? Estimula competências de ação? Outras?
- 3.4 Até que ponto a AFC tem sido bem-sucedida e eficaz em trazer mudanças transformadoras, nomeadamente na área da educação para a sustentabilidade?

4. Conclusões e perspetivas futuras

- 4.1 Na perspetiva da DGE, que fatores têm favorecido e criado barreiras à implementação, integração e sustentabilidade da AFC nas escolas? Que exemplos/ indicações pode dar, sobre a forma como essas barreiras foram/ estão/ irão ser enfrentadas?
- 4.2 Como pode a AFC ser alargada a mais escolas? Que mecanismos já existem ou estão a ser pensados para favorecer esse alargamento?
- 4.3 Quais são os principais pontos fortes e fracos da AFC?
- 4.4 De que forma o contexto nacional impacta na eficácia e sustentabilidade da AFC?
- 4.5 Como pode a AFC ser melhorada? Quais os desafios à sua continuidade - desafios de gestão (por exemplo, como garantir o financiamento?) - e desafios substanciais (por exemplo, como garantir um impacto positivo?). Que oportunidades/ soluções estão a ser equacionadas para superar esses desafios?
- 4.6 Qual o potencial de transferibilidade da AFC? Há evidências da sua utilidade/ aplicabilidade a outros contextos/ países? Que limitações identifica? Como podem ser superadas?

¹ a) *Sobre*: conteúdo abordado; b) *Em*: ambiente envolvente; c) *Através*: definindo a cultura, e.x. aprendizagem através da paz, pela criação de aulas pacíficas, pelo cuidado, *whole school approach* com valores, etc.; d) *Para*: aprendizagem ativa, pensamento crítico, pensamento futurista e pensamento sistémico.

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4.7 Que lições-chave podem ser extraídas deste período de implementação da AFC, que possam ser valiosas para a sua aplicação noutros contextos/ países/ níveis de educação?

4.8 Que comentários e informações/ conclusões pode ainda fornecer para explicar melhor o contexto em que a AFC opera e que a torna bem-sucedida?

Muito obrigado pela sua colaboração e ajuda neste estudo!

Alexandra Silva (diretora da associação The K-Evolution), alexandra.silva@kevolution.org

Rita Fouto (sócia-gerente da FAREDUCA - Educação para a Sustentabilidade),

fareduca.geral@gmail.com

Antje Disterheft (investigadora no CENSE, FCT NOVA, Universidade NOVA de Lisboa),

a.disterheft@fct.unl.pt

ANNEX IV - Focus Group Presentation

PPMi

**Estudo Europeu sobre a Educação para a Sustentabilidade Ambiental (Education for Environmental Sustainability (EES)):
Caso de Estudo Português sobre a Autonomia e Flexibilidade Curricular (AFC)**

Grupo focal
19 de maio de 2023, 14 – 15:30

Investigadoras / facilitadoras:
Alexandra Silva (K-evolution)
Anja Distelhaft (CENSE, FCT NOVA)
Rita Fouto (FAREDUCA)

Agenda

- Aspectos administrativos
- Apresentação
- Enquadramento do grupo focal no estudo e objetivos
- Diálogo
- Reflexão final

Study on Education for Environmental Sustainability (EES) (2020)/Comissão Europeia | Grupo focal sobre a AFC em Portugal e o seu potencial para a EES (2023)

Aspectos administrativos

Agradecemos muito a sua disponibilidade para participar neste estudo. Garantimos que todos os dados recolhidos serão anonimizados e respetam todas as normas da privacidade e da proteção de dados, definidas pela Comissão Europeia. A gravação deste grupo focal serve apenas para a transcrição e análise dos aspetos chave do debate. Os dados serão destruídos no fim do estudo.

Agradecemos a sua assinatura para o consentimento da sua participação neste estudo.

Por favor confirme também verbalmente que concorda com a gravação desta sessão.

Study on Education for Environmental Sustainability (EES) (2020)/Comissão Europeia | Grupo focal sobre a AFC em Portugal e o seu potencial para a EES (2023)

Apresentação

- Por favor, apresente-se com o seu nome, a sua afiliação profissional e atual função / papel profissional.

Study on Education for Environmental Sustainability (EES) (2020)/Comissão Europeia | Grupo focal sobre a AFC em Portugal e o seu potencial para a EES (2023)

Enquadramento e objetivos

- ◊ Estudo pedido pela Comissão Europeia (DG EAC) no âmbito das reflexões sobre uma Europa Verde e Sustentável (Pacto Ecológico / European Green Deal) e como a educação pode ajudar a atingir os objetivos associados (para neutralidade carbónica até 2050).
- ◊ Estudo liderado pelo centro de investigação europeu PPMi e em cooperação com a European Schoolnet, a decorrer desde Janeiro até finais de Junho 2022.
- ◊ Os objetivos centrais deste estudo são:
 - ◊ Investigar e "mapear" as políticas e abordagens nacionais e institucionais da Educação para a Sustentabilidade Ambiental (EES) nos 27 Estados-membros da União Europeia;
 - ◊ Identificar as condições sistémicas, barreiras e fatores promotores para desenvolver a EES em todos os níveis de escolaridade
 - ◊ Analisar boas práticas e entender melhor o seu potencial para "scaling up" em políticas nacionais e europeias.

Study on Education for Environmental Sustainability (EES) (2020)/Comissão Europeia | Grupo focal sobre a AFC em Portugal e o seu potencial para a EES (2023)

O Estudo Europeu sobre a EES

Tarefa 1

- Análise de documentos sobre as políticas e práticas relacionadas com a EES nos 27 estados-membros da UE, seguida de iniciativas para casos de estudos
- 27 relatórios de perfil de cada país da UE
- Lista com 100 iniciativas (27 foram apresentadas à CE, 5 foram escolhidas)

Tarefa 2

- Caso de estudo com análise de documentos, entrevistas e grupo focal sobre a iniciativa selecionada:
 - ➔ a AFC em Portugal e o seu potencial contributo para a EES

Tarefa 3

- Grupo focal com peritos na área de educação nos 27 estados-membros
- Relatório final para a Comissão Europeia (DG EAC)

Study on Education for Environmental Sustainability (EES) (2020)/Comissão Europeia | Grupo focal sobre a AFC em Portugal e o seu potencial para a EES (2023)

Resultados preliminares sobre a AFC

Análise SWOT (selecção)	
Pontos fortes Visão Política Colaboração e Partilha Interdisciplinaridade e transdisciplinaridade	Oportunidades ODS UNESCO (ODS for 2030 + Roadmap) Whole-School Approach Empoderamento dos Alunos
Pontos fracos Demasiado liberal Falta de recursos humanos e financeiros ODS nos currículos - foco nas ciências naturais	Ameaças Resistências duradouras (conservadorismo e manual-dependência) Capacidades intrínsecas (massa crítica) Interlocutar ODS

Study on Education for Environmental Sustainability (SES) (ipgms) / Comissão Europeia | Grupo focal sobre a AFC em Portugal e o seu potencial para a SES | 10/2024 | 11

Diálogo

Por favor, seguem sempre as regras básicas:

- Respeitem o ponto de vista de cada um / a, mesmo quando discordam;
 - Não se interrompem uns aos outros;
 - Utilize uma linguagem respeitosa quando partilhem uma perspetiva oposta;
 - Não há "uma verdade"; não há respostas ou perceções erradas.
- Study on Education for Environmental Sustainability (SES) (ipgms) / Comissão Europeia | Grupo focal sobre a AFC em Portugal e o seu potencial para a SES | 10/2024 | 12

Diálogo

- 1ª parte:

Que fatores-chave identificam na AFC que sejam promotores de uma educação para a sustentabilidade (no entendimento alargado, incluindo a cidadania)?

Que processos de mudança a AFC introduziu que sejam relevantes, por exemplo, para impulsionar os ODS?*

(*Objetivos para o Desenvolvimento Sustentável)

Study on Education for Environmental Sustainability (SES) (ipgms) / Comissão Europeia | Grupo focal sobre a AFC em Portugal e o seu potencial para a SES | 10/2024 | 13

Diálogo

- 2ª parte

Segundo a vossa experiência, como é que a AFC pode potenciar uma visão de escola integral (*whole-school approach*) e uma aprendizagem holística para a sustentabilidade? Que exemplos podem dar?

Study on Education for Environmental Sustainability (SES) (ipgms) / Comissão Europeia | Grupo focal sobre a AFC em Portugal e o seu potencial para a SES | 10/2024 | 14

Reflexões finais

- Qual a vossa visão sobre o potencial de escalabilidade (*"scaling up"*) das práticas relacionadas com a AFC?
- Study on Education for Environmental Sustainability (SES) (ipgms) / Comissão Europeia | Grupo focal sobre a AFC em Portugal e o seu potencial para a SES | 10/2024 | 15

PPMi

Muito obrigada pela sua participação!

Alexandra Silva (K-evolution)
Antje Disterheft (CENSE, FCT NOVA)
Rita Fouto (FAREDUCA)

K-Evolution | FAREDUCA | CENSE | FCT NOVA

CENSE | FAREDUCA